

HUMAN CAPITAL MANAGEMENT MODELS.

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***ABSTRACT** Human capital management is a systematic approach aimed at effective management of the organization's labor resources, development of their potential and adaptation to the strategic goals of the enterprise. This article analyzes the main models of human capital management, including the Harvard model, AMO (Ability, Motivation and Capabilities), standard cause model of HRM, HR value chain, guest model. Each model provides a different approach to workforce engagement, motivation, performance, and development processes. The advantages and disadvantages of these models are analyzed and their relevance for modern organizations is highlighted. The role of human capital in increasing innovation, organizational flexibility and competitiveness is emphasized. The results serve to better understand the possibilities of maximum use of human capital in the global market.*

***KEYWORDS:** HRM, AMO, HR, ROI, Empirical, Harvard, Stakeholders*

I. INTRODUCTION.

The success of modern organizations is closely related to the effective management of human resources. The Human Resources Management (HRM) system is important for achieving the organization's strategic goals and ensuring its sustainable development. And the HR model is a set of theoretical and practical approaches that help to form, plan and develop this system.[1]

The HR model allows the organization to effectively manage such processes as personnel selection, their development, motivation, performance evaluation and improvement of the working environment. The correct selection and application of this model has a positive effect not only on increasing the work efficiency of

employees, but also on the overall success of the enterprise. Organizations can use different HR models to form a management system that matches their specific needs and goals.

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The economic literature on the evaluation of human capital is extensive, and various models and theories have been developed by a number of prominent economists in this field.

Theodore Schultz: Schultz was one of the founders of human capital theory, which studied how investments in education and human resources affect economic growth. His work "Investment in Human Capital: The Role of Education and of Research" is one of the important works in this field.[2]

Through this book, Schultz analyzes the impact of education and scientific research on economic growth. It considers investment in human capital as one of society's most important resources. Education is seen as an investment in human capital, increasing the income of individuals in the labor market. A well-educated workforce is faster to adopt innovations and adopt new technologies. Countries with insufficient investment in human capital lag behind in economic development. Investing in education and health can be a tool to reduce poverty.

This work of Schultz made a great contribution to the analysis of the role of human capital in the economy. His research was later developed by Gary Becker, Jacob Mincer and other scientists. Investing in human capital is one of the important directions of economic policy even today.[3]

Gary Becker (Gary Becker): Becker expanded the concept of human capital and analyzed the economic value of education, health and other human factors. His book Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis is a classic work on the subject. This book was first published in 1964, later reprinted several times and had a great impact on economics.

Becker considers human capital as an economic resource like physical capital (machines, buildings and other means of production). Education, health, training and migration are investments in human capital. These investments increase labor productivity and lead to increased incomes. Becker also studies the decisions of families to invest in human capital.

III. METHODS

What is an HR model? It is a set of strategic approaches, principles and processes that define how an organization implements HR management. It is designed to create an effective system for managing and developing employees.

1. Harvard Model (Harvard Model)

The Harvard model of HRM is associated with the contributions of Michael Beer in 1984 and Paauve and Richardson in 1997. This model emphasizes human resource management with a long-term and comprehensive approach to personnel management.

Five main components:

- *External influence factors* (Economic, social, political and legal environment)
- *Organizational Stakeholders* (Employers, Employees, Trade Unions and Government)
- *Human resources policy selection* (Recruitment, training, motivation and personnel policy)
- *HR results* (loyalty, efficiency, professional development)
- *Long-term results* (Social well-being, economic efficiency, organizational success)

The Harvard Model of HRM

Figure 1. The Harvard Model of HRM

Table 1

Advantages:	Disadvantages:
It is aimed at improving the well-being of employees	It does not always give quick results, it takes a long time
Allows you to create a long-term HR strategy	The development of the HR department is necessary for implementation
It allows to adapt the HR policy to the external and internal environment	It may be suitable for large organizations, but it may be difficult to use in small businesses
It serves to increase the level of job satisfaction of employees	

2. AMO Model

AMO model-An organization that takes into account the ability, motivation and capabilities of an employee can achieve its goals more easily, because it helps to

improve the performance of its employees. Organizational leaders can use this model to influence the performance of employees.

HR professionals can use a person's ability (A), motivation (M) and capabilities (O) to measure their performance (P). We can express this information with the following equation:

$$P = AMO \quad (1)$$

This model includes three important factors of HR management:

- Ability - improving the skills and knowledge of employees
- Motivation - increasing the motivation of workers to work
- Opportunity - creating conditions for employees to show their potential

Figure 2. Workplace Performance

Table 2

Advantages:	Disadvantages:
It is aimed at improving the development and efficiency of employees	It takes time and resources to plan and implement an HR strategy
It allows to form the HR strategy based on specific factors	Not a one-size-fits-all solution for every organization – needs to be adapted to different environments

Increases productivity by increasing employee motivation	Motivation and opportunities may depend on external factors
An effective model for long-term results	

3. Standard Causal Model of HRM

The standard causal model of HRM derives from many similar models published in the 1990s and early 2000s. According to this model, HR is effective only if its strategy is aligned with the business strategy.[4]

Standart Causal Model of HRM

Figure 3. Standart Casual Model of HRM

The model shows the causal chain of how HR processes affect the organization. The chain starts with the company's overall business strategy, which influences HR strategy and processes.

For example, hiring, training, evaluation, and compensation practices can lead to outcomes such as commitment, quality products, and commitment. These HRM results lead to improved internal performance, which in turn affects financial results (such as profits, turnover, better margins and ROI).

This HR system also shows that the relationships in the model are not always one-sided. Some HR practices can directly lead to improved internal performance. For example, good training can directly lead to better performance without affecting HR results.

Table 3

Advantages:	Disadvantages:
It helps to clearly analyze the results of HR policy	It cannot always give direct results, external factors also play a role
It allows planning strategic decisions related to HRM	Personal aspects of employees (personality, culture, personal motivation) can have unexpected effects on HRM results.
Shows the connection between employee motivation and the overall development of the organization	Requires a highly planned HRM policy

4. HR value chain

- The HR value chain is one of the most popular models in HR. It builds on the work of Paauwe and Richardson (1997). According to the HR value chain, everything that HR does and measures can be divided into two categories:

- HRM activities: day-to-day activities, including recruiting, compensation, training, and succession planning. This activity is often measured using HR metrics. These are called performance indicators.

-HRM Outcomes: The objectives that HRM activities try to achieve. We hire, train and compensate for specific goals or outcomes. These outcomes include employee satisfaction, motivation, retention and availability.

HR Value Chain

Figure 4. HR Value Chain

If we only focus on measuring HRM performance, we automatically prioritize efficiency gains over cost reduction. However, this may not yield the best long-term results. Instead, we should focus on measuring the results of HRM because it helps align our processes with our goals.

For example, we prefer to spend a few more days hiring a new employee (time to hire, an efficiency measure) if he is a better fit for the company (hire quality, an outcome measure). The goal should be to put the best person in the right position.[5]

There is also another effect. If the efficiency of the company is high, the HRM activity will also increase. This is because more profitable companies typically invest more in HR software.

Table 4

Advantages:	Disadvantages:
Enables linking HR strategy with business results	HRM outcomes can be difficult to measure

Assists in effective evaluation and improvement of HR practices	It is not a universal system suitable for every organization
It serves to increase the motivation and productivity of employees	It requires a long-term analysis
A useful model for explaining the importance of the HRM department to the organization's management	

5. Guest model

The Guest model was developed by David Guest, a professor at King's Business School in the UK in the late 1980s and 1990s. This can mean the model used in HR systems for temporary or visiting workers (contractors, freelancers, interns). Such a system has the following characteristics:

Temporary or visiting staff (for example, project-based professionals or consultants).

Limited permissions – visiting employees may have more limited access to company resources than regular employees.[6]

Guest Model

Figure 5. Guest Model

Fundamentally, HRM begins with specific strategies aligned with business objectives; which in turn inform HRM practices and policies, lead to specific HRM outcomes, lead to desired employee behaviors such as commitment and motivation, lead to collaborative outcomes lead to financial results.[7]

Table 5

Features	Harvard Model	AMO Model	Standart Causal Model of HRM	HR value chain	Guest model
The main idea	HRM policy and stakeholder balance	Dependence of employees on Ability, Motivation and Opportunity factors	Influencing the organization through HRM policy and management actions	HRM practices determine the value added to the organization	HRM should be a strategic part of the organization
Focus	Balance between long-term HRM policies and stakeholders	Development of employees' skills, motivation and capabilities	Causality of HRM activities to organizational results	The relationship between HRM practices and business results	Ensuring the long-term success of the organization through a strategic HRM approach
Components	-HRM policy - Influence of employees on decisions -Long-term HR results	- Ability - Motivation - Opportunity	-HRM Policies and Practices - Employee Reactions - Employee Behaviors -Business Outcomes	-HR Inputs -HR Processes -HR Outputs -Business Outputs	-HRM Strategies -HRM Practices -HR Outcomes -Employee Behavior -Financial Performance
The role of employees	An important resource and stakeholder of the organization	Key contributors to HR results	Influences organizational results through behavior	A key resource in value creation	Their development directly depends on the success of the organization
The role of HR strategy	Keng qamrovli, uzoq muddatli rejalash	Comprehensive, long-term planning	The reaction of employees depends on the results	Business results are shaped through HRM processes	HRM strategy should be an integral part of business strategy
Impact on the organization	Long-term efficiency and increase of social responsibility of the organization	Improving productivity through employee development	It directly affects the productivity of employees and the results of the organization	Shows the relevance of HRM strategies to business results	Defines HRM as an important part of strategic management

RESULTS:

A Comparison of HRM Models

Table 6

Model	Role in global market conditions	Strengths	Disadvantages
Harvard Model	Helps align the organization's HR policies with global market trends and stakeholder needs.	Employee s-Forms long-term HR strategies. - Maintains a balance between employees, management and stakeholders. - Combines HRM with business strategy.	- Adapting HR policies to international markets can be difficult. - It requires taking into account the labor legislation of each country.
AMO Model	It is aimed at developing the skills, motivation and capabilities of employees to be competitive in the global environment.	Employee s - Helps to increase the efficiency of employees. -Enables adaptation to developing and changing market conditions. - Compatible with international workforce management.	- Because it is based on only three main factors (ability,motivation,opportunity),it does not sufficiently consider other external factors. - It requires an individual approach in the conditions of the global labor market.

<p>Standart Causal Model of HRM</p>	<p>It allows to analyze how HRM activities influence the results of the global market.</p>	<p>-It allows to evaluate the effectiveness of HRM strategies. -Explains the causal relationship between HR activities and business results. -Suitable for analysis of international HR strategies.</p>	<p>-Measuring HRM results is difficult. -Each region may have different results, as HR strategies may change in different cultural and economic contexts.</p>
<p>HR qiymat zanjiri</p>	<p>Helps determine how HRM strategies can add value to an organization in a global market.</p>	<p>-Aimed at increasing the economic efficiency of HRM. -Allows optimization of HR activities at the international level. -Helps measure the impact of HR investments on business results.</p>	<p>-HRM requires accurate financial indicators for proper evaluation of activities. -Implementing HR practices in a global market can be difficult.</p>

<p>Mehmon modeli</p>	<p>Defines HRM as a strategic tool for global companies and improves the effectiveness of international HR policies.</p>	<p>-Increases the impact of HRM on business results. -Helps adapt HR strategies to international market requirements -Makes HRM the main pillar of the organization at the international level.</p>	<p>-Development and implementation of HRM strategy takes a long time. -Since each global market is unique, developing a common strategy can be complicated.</p>
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Figure 6. The relevance of HRM Models in 2020-2025. (This information is based on global trends and strategic development of HRM)¹

¹ <https://www.nbcnews.com/business/economy>

The graph above shows the increasing relevance of HRM models in 2020-2025.

Analysis: The Harvard model has the highest relevance, reaching 83% by 2025. The AMO model is growing steadily because it focuses on employee motivation and ability.[8] The Standard Causal Model has continued relevance because it examines the relationship between HRM outcomes and business success. The guest model is also growing steadily due to its focus on strategic HRM.

IV. CONCLUSION.

- The Harvard model focuses on stakeholders and long-term HR strategy.
- The AMO model is based on improving results through the ability, motivation and capabilities of employees.
- Standard Causal Model (Causal Model of HRM) explains the causal relationship between HRM practices, employee reactions and organizational results.
- The HR Value Chain shows step-by-step how HRM practices impact business results.
- Guest model considers HRM as strategic management of the organization and emphasizes long-term development.

Each model can be applied to different organizations and HR strategies. The organization should choose the appropriate model depending on its goals and resources.

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